

A NOVEL ARCHITECTURE OF LOW-POWER AND HIGH-SPEED SENSE AMPLIFIER BASED FLIP-FLOP IN SAPON STYLE

Ram Yadav¹, Pallavee Jaiswal²

¹*Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Dr. C. V. Raman University, India*

²*Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Dr. C. V. Raman University, India*

Abstract

This paper proposes a novel design of sense amplifier-based flip-flop (SAFF) in SAPON style suitable for low-power and high-speed operation using 45nm MTCMOS technology. Stackly Arranged low Power ON transistor (SAPON) technique along with Multi-Threshold-CMOS (MTCMOS) provides better power reduction and low voltage operation than existing standard reduction techniques. Hence, named the proposed design as SAPON-SAFF. Tanner's EDA tool is used to run the simulation. Post layout simulation results shows that the proposed SAPON-SAFF achieves a 73.98% reduction in power consumption than the conventional SAFF (CONV-SAFF). Also, a very low CK-Q Delay and Power-Delay Product (PDP), is achieved compared to CONV-SAFF and other existing SAFFs.

Keywords:

Sense Amplifier based Flip-Flop (SAFF), MTCMOS, SAPON.

1. INTRODUCTION

Power & speed efficient are the prerequisite of integrated circuit (IC) design. A flip-flop (FF) is the basic memory element of an IC, so the delay and power consumption of the FFs precisely determines the power consumption and the performance of an IC.

As per [2], FFs contribute a substantial portion of the power intake in the digital system. Therefore, augmenting the delay and power of FFs can rightly mend the performance and lessen the power consumption of digital systems.

Sense-amplifier-based flip-flop (SAFF) is one of the efficient low-power flip-flops which is widely used in low power circuits. The SAFF, first introduced in [1], is a fast flip-flop with a negative or near-zero setup time. Hence, SAFF is considered to improve the performance in terms of high speed and reduced power intake of the digital circuit.

Basically, SAFF is a type of master-slave flip-flop (MSFF) and a conventional SAFF (CONV-SAFF) is composed of a Sense-Amplifier (SA) stage and a Slave R-S Latch [3], as shown in Fig.1. SAFF design provides nearly zero set-up time and lower clock skew. Its SA stage could record the data right after Clock's (CK) rising edge, and its output could be maintained as the state of SN and RN throughout CK's positive half cycle. With a negative or near-zero setup time and a lower hold time, the SAFF

can be considered as a good alternative to MSFF in the cell library for high-speed operation.

But the low-voltage performance of CONV-SAFF greatly limits its operation range, so a lot of effort has been made to improve the performance of CONV-SAFF. Several improved SAFF designs have been proposed over CONV-SAFF, some important findings are Nikolic's SAFF [3], Kim's SAFF [4], Strollo's SAFF [5], Ahmadi's SAFF [6], Lin's SAFF [9], Jeong's SAFF [11], Heng's SAFF [14], Yuan's SAFF [18].

This paper proposes a novel SAFF design based on the analysis of the above structures of SAFF. In our proposed design, we are modifying Yuan's SAFF [18] by employing the SAPON (Stackly Arranged low Power ON transistor) technique of [19] to mitigate power consumption and delay of the circuit than the existing techniques. Thus named our proposed design as SAPON-SAFF.

Furthermore, to overcome the problem of power consumption without impacting delay and to provide robust operation even at supply voltage below 1.0 Volt, the proposed SAPON-SAFF is optimized with Multi Threshold CMOS (MTCMOS) logic in place of CMOS. MTCMOS stands for "Multi-Threshold Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor", which is a power-saving technique used in modern ICs to reduce static power consumption when the circuits are in standby mode [14]. The MTCMOS technique is commonly employed in mobile devices and other battery-powered systems to enhance energy efficiency and prolong battery life.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in Section (2) Overview of existing SAFFs; in Section (3) Structure and Working of the proposed SAPON-SAFF; in Section (4) Simulation results and comparisons with CONV-SAFF; and finally, Section 5 draws conclusion, declaration and references.

2. OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SAFF ARCHITECTURES

Like MSFF, SAFF is composed of a Sense-Amplifier (SA) stage and a Slave Latch [14]. The schematic of the conventional SAFF (CONV-SAFF) [18], composed of a SA stage and a NAND2-based set-reset (S-R) latch stage, is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Conventional SAFF (CONV-SAFF)

2.1 WORKING OF A SAFF:

Basically, SAFF operates as follows:

A sense amplifier speeds memory operation by sensing small initial changes in the data line and driving the stored value to the output quickly. [2].

In SAFF, the SA stage could record data right after Clock's (CK) rising edge, and its output could be maintained throughout CK's positive half cycle. [14].

The SA stage produces monotonous transitions from High to Low logic level on one of the outputs (SN or RN), following the rising edge of clock (CK). And the slave S-R latch captures each transition and holds the state until the next rising edge of CK arrives. In this way, the whole structure acts as a flip-flop. [18].

Consider Fig.1; when the CK is low, the SN and RN nodes are pre-charged through transistors (being PMOS type), MP1 and MP4, to the supply voltage, VDD. At the next rising edge of the CK, the transistors MP1 and MP4 are turned OFF; and MN6 (being NMOS type) is turned ON; which makes the CONV-SAFF sample the voltage of the input D and change the voltage at nodes SN or RN i.e., one of the pre-charge nodes (SN and RN) is discharged to zero while the other node remains VDD, depending on the input data applied at node D. The transition from output Q and QN to the supply voltage's high (VDD) or low (VSS), depends on the state of the nodes RN and SN, which drive the slave S-R latch. The always-ON transistor MN3 provides alternate path and maintain the output of the SA through SN and RN state, when CK is high. For example, at the rising edge of CK in response to input D = 1, the SN node discharged to '0' needs to be maintained at '0' during the positive half cycle of CK. And if the input D changes to '0' during the positive half cycle of CK, then another path to '0' (i.e., ground GND) should be provided to SN, and hence

transistor MN3 works at this time. In this way SA of CONV-SAFF functions.

The main trouble with the CONV-SAFF is the unbalanced transition delay of Q and QN of the S-R latch because of which the speed of the CONV-SAFF is greatly limited. Apart from this, the unbalanced transition delay also creates a glitch in the data path, increasing total power consumption. [14]. Also, the large power requirement of the pre-charge operation adds to the total power consumption. Moreover, the always-ON transistor decreases the robustness of the SAFF at low supply voltages. [18].

To overcome all these flaws, several improved SAFF designs have been proposed over CONV-SAFF, some important findings are discussed.

2.2 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SAFFS:

In [3], Nikolic et al. proposed a SAFF with improved latch while retaining the SA stage as that of CONV-SAFF. The latch design comprises of two inverters with several complex logics, to exclude the delay dependence between Q and QN as in the CONV-SAFF, and to reduce the delay of the SAFF. The schematic of Nikolic's latch is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Nikolic's Latch

In [3], the inversion of SN and RN are carried out in the latch stage to make four signals as SN, RN, S and R. These signals are used to generate the outputs Q and QN directly. Thus, the delay dependence between Q and QN is eliminated and the CK-to-Q delay is reduced. But, because of the complex logic of the design and the delay introduced of the inverters cannot be ignored, the optimization of the delay may not meet the expectations.

In [4], Kim et al. introduced a SAFF with similar SA stage of CONV-SAFF but with improvised latch consisting of two N-C²MOS circuits along with two pairs of back-to-back inverters to achieve the fast transition as shown in Fig. 3.

However, [4] has two drawbacks: (1) When the input D and the previous state of output Q are both high, then the output Q must remain high at the next rising edge of CK, but because of the incompleteness of discharge of the node SN, the pull-down

path of Q is ON, from which a glitch occurs; (2) The back-to-back inverter at the output Q generate contention current, which raise the power consumption and the delay.

Fig.3. Kim's Latch

In [5], Strollo et al. introduced a SAFF combining the CONV-SAFF with Kim's SAFF to attain both fast and glitch-free operation. The schematic of Strollo's SAFF is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Strollo's SAFF: (a) SA stage (b) Latch stage

In [5], to reduce the power consumption and D-to-Q latency, they drive the symmetric latch directly with only SN and RN, removing their inversion signals (S & N).

Even with the power reduction by this modification, a signal conflict in the latching stage can be observed resulting in increased latency. For example, if input = 1 (high) arrives when Q = 0 (low), during the period in which QN is being pulled down through M19-M21 after the rising clock edge, M16 stays ON and struggles against the pull-down of QN unless SN is discharged to raise Q; this will result in a longer falling latency of the outputs. Moreover, the problem related to always ON transistor (M4 here) like Nikolic's SAFF [3], still causes increment in power consumption, latency, and area.

In [6], Ahmadi et al. instead of modifying latch in CONV-SAFF, improves the SA stage by adding the delay transistor in it, equating the rise and fall delays of the node SN and RN.

In [9], Lin et al. improved the latch of [4] to a single-ended structure while retaining SA as of CONV-SAFF. Lin's Latch is shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5. Lin's Latch

In [9], since there are few logics in the latch stage between SN and the output Q, hence the delay and the power consumption of this kind of SAFF is greatly eased compared to CONV-SAFF. Despite this, there occurs a big glitch when both, the output Q and the succeeding data input, are high; and this glitch will promote the power consumption in the SAFF. Moreover, the current contention in the latch because of the back-to-back inverters will add to the power intake too.

As per [11], all the SAFFs [3]-[6], [9], employing the SA stage of CONV-SAFF, suffers from the difficulty of low voltage operation and the reason behind it is the always-ON transistor MN3 of the SA stage of CONV-SAFF shown in Fig.1.

To address this problem, Jeong et al. in [11] proposed a SAFF with transition completion detection (SAFF-TCD) i.e., TC signal applied to always-ON transistor (MN6, here) shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6. Jeong's SAFF (a) SA (b) Latch

SAFF-TCD [11] knock out the problem related to the shorting device through always-ON transistor (MN6, here), by detecting the transitions of SN and RN. So, when CK=0, both SN and RN are pre-charged to high, making transition completion signal TC be low and transistor MN6 be OFF. Thus, the pull-down evaluation of SN or RN is individually performed,

and therefore, overcomes the sizing issue of MN6. After the pull-down of SN or RN, TC turns high to drive MN6 ON for static operation.

Although SAFF-TCD can avoid the sizing issue of MN6, but the power consumption and latency show limited advancements over Strollo's SAFF, as mentioned in [11].

In [14], Heng et al. observed that, during the pre-charge operation the SA stage of the CONV-SAFF required to charge all its internal nodes (such as N1, N2, and N3 in Fig.1), and the nodes are discharged to VSS (i.e., low) during the data-capturing operation, irrespective of the input data. Also, the pre-charging of nodes N1, N2 and N3 do not influence the function of the SA stage and thus, [14] regarded pre-charging of these nodes as a waste of power. So, [14] carried out a conditional cut-off strategy in the latch to break power supply at these nodes during pre-charge phase to get a glitch-free and contention-free operation.

Fig.7. Heng's SAFF: (a) SA (b) Latch

[14] improvised the structure of the SA by adding two NMOS transistors (MN5 & MN6) regulated by CK, as shown in Fig.7. Due to this improvisation, the transistors MN5 and MN6 are OFF when CK is low and thus the nodes (N1 and N2) related to transistors (MN3 and MN4) are no longer needed to be pre-charged during the operation. Thus, the power requirement of the pre-charge operation is considerably lowered and of the proposed SAFF.

In the latch stage of proposed SAFF, [14] merged the benefits of Strollo's latch [5] and Lin's latch [9] to carry out fast and energy efficient operation. Moreover, to provide low voltage operation, the proposed SAFF of [14] adopted MTCMOS optimization in place of CMOS.

But, in [14], further reduction in power consumption can be achieved by preventing transition leakage. Hence, discussed in our proposed design.

In [18], Yuan et al. proposed a SAFF in 55nm CMOS technology by modifying both the SA stage and the latch, as shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8. Yuan's SAFF

As per [18], the cause of continuous power consumption in the SA stage is the pre-charge of SN and RN to VDD every time when CK is low until the input D switches. To avoid it, [18] introduced two transistors, MP5 and MP6 in the proposed design to cooperate with MN4 and MN5, which results in the controlled pre-charge of the SN and RN as determined by the switching operation of the input D and not by CK. Thus, avoiding the continuous charge and discharge of SN and RN with the CK transition while the input remains unchanged for a long time, avoiding additional power consumption overhead.

In [18], the proposed latch structure, the leakage current is reduced with the insertion of the MP7, MN7, and MN10 as shown in Fig.7. The inverter-like structure design ensures the node's fast charge, and the pull-down path design with shut-off transistor MN10, reduces the leakage current and ensures the correct function of the latch structure.

Although, Yuan's SAFF [18] provided a solution to continuous pre-charge power consumption but, it is observed that the switching and short-circuit leakage power plays a significant role in the high-frequency dynamic transition of inputs. So, to effectively control the leakage power due to transition, the arrangement should be provided within the SA stage also rather than only in the slave latch of a SAFF. Also, [18] proposed the design in CMOS, which may suffer from the difficulty of low voltage operation.

Thus, it can be concluded as, most of the SAFF design suffers either of the (a) low voltage operation problem, (b) continuous pre-charge power consumption, (c) leakage current arising out of switching, short-circuit and data transition, (d) increased delay.

3. PROPOSED SAFF: ARCHITECTURE AND WORKING

We propose a novel design of SAFF to overcome all these problems. In our proposed design, we are modifying Yuan's SAFF [18] by employing the SAPON technique of [19] along

with MTCMOS optimization, to mitigate leakage current, power consumption, delay, and low voltage operation of the design. Thus named our proposed design as SAPON-SAFF, its schematic is shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9. Schematic of the proposed SAPON-SAFF

Because the data transition occurs in the SA stage, an arrangement for the leakage current control is provided in the SA stage in our proposed SAPON-SAFF to mitigate the power consumption. Furthermore, to overcome the problem of power consumption without impacting delay and to provide robust operation even at supply voltages as low as 0.4 V, the Multi Threshold CMOS (MTCMOS) logic is used. Therefore, the proposed SAFF is optimized with MTCMOS (Multi Threshold CMOS) instead of CMOS.

3.1 SAPON TECHNIQUE:

Switching and short-circuit leakage power plays a significant role in the high-frequency dynamic transition of inputs. To lessen power consumption of the CMOS based logic circuit, [19] proposed a new power reduction technique calling it the SAPON i.e., Stackly Arranged low Power ON transistor technique. As per [19], SAPON provides better power reduction than existing standard reduction techniques.

In this SAPON technique, the resistance between the supply voltage (VDD) and ground (GND), is controlled by connecting two leakage-control transistors outside the logic; thereby prevents the leakage current from a short circuit during the changeover stage. In addition, it uses CMOS SAPON transistors connected in series between VDD and GND, to manage the sub threshold leakage current during the leveling phase. Consequently, it produces desired results while yet using little power.

Take an example of CMOS inverter as shown in Fig. 10(a) which then optimized with SAPON technique in Fig. 10(b) to discuss the SAPON approach.

A typical CMOS inverter contains a PMOS (Q1) and an NMOS (Q2) transistor connected in series, where the supply VDD and ground (GND) are connected to the source terminal of the PMOS and NMOS transistors respectively. Input (IN) is connected to the Gate terminals and Output (OUT) is obtained at the Drain terminals as shown in Fig. 8(a).

Fig.10(a). CMOS Inverter

Fig. 10(b), shows the SAPON technique implemented over Fig. 10(a).

Fig.10(b). CMOS Inverter optimized with SAPON technique

In the SAPON technique, the logic block contains two SAPON transistors (PMOS and NMOS) whose gate terminal is connected to the GND and VDD respectively, which operates in the active region. SAPON PMOS (Q3) is placed above the pull-up network and SAPON NMOS (Q4) is placed below the pull-down network as shown in Fig. 10(b). As per [19], this stack arrangement lessens the power consumption of circuits while serving the purpose than the existing techniques.

In Fig.10(b), when logic 0 is given as input, PMOS (Q1) in the pull-up network is ON, NMOS (Q2) in the pull-down network is OFF while the SAPON transistors (Q3 and Q4) remain in the active region. Therefore, output reads 1; serving the purpose of an Inverter. Similarly for logic 1, PMOS in the pull-up network is OFF, NMOS in the pull-down network is ON and the output gets pulled down to 0.

Table.1. Truth Table of SAPON Inverter

Input	PMOS	NMOS	SAPON Transistors	Output
0	ON	OFF	ON	1
1	OFF	ON	ON	0

These two SAPON transistors need to operate in an active region which in turn makes them active in all phases. And, as per [19], it provides desirable output by maintaining low power consumption across circuits.

In this way the approach can be concluded as the arrangement in which the gate terminal of PMOS is wired with the GND of NMOS and at the end of NMOS, its gate terminal is wired with the VDD, the supply terminal. This approach is known as SAPON approach.

3.2 PROPOSED SAPON-SAFF WORKING:

SAPON approach in SAFF serves the purpose of prevention of short-circuit leakage arising during transition period in the SA stage and thus the reduction in power consumption is achieved while maintaining desired function of SAFF.

As per [19], short-circuit leakage plays a considerable impact on dynamic power consumption of a CMOS circuit. During the transition, there exists a period in which the voltage of the gates of transistors in a CMOS circuit, is between the threshold of PMOS and NMOS, such that it switches ON both the transistors and thus, a conducting path like short-circuit is formed directly from the VDD to GND which leads to the power dissipation. In the proposed technique called SAPON, two leakage-control transistors PMOS (MTP) and NMOS (MTN), are built outside the logic circuit which effectively increases the resistance between VDD and GND during the transition phase and thus resists the short-circuit leakage.

Fig.11(a). SA stage of the proposed SAPON-SAFF

Consider Fig.11(a), whenever logic '1' is given as input to the gate terminal of NMOS (MTN), it will turn ON and when logic '0' is given as input to the gate terminal of PMOS (MTP), it will turn ON.

In Fig.11(a), initially both MTP AND MTN are in ON state because wired path $ae=1$ is supplied to MTN with VDD connection and wired path $fb=0$ is supplied to MTP with GND connection.

So, during transition period when the logic circuit (here Yuan's SAFF [18] employed) conducts, therefore logic '1' reaches at node 'd' of MTN. As MTN is in ON state because node 'e' at its gate, is wired to VDD; the logic '1' reaches to node 'f' and thus, through path 'fb', logic '1' is applied on MTP which turns PMOS (MTP) to OFF and cut-off the supply VDD from the circuit. In this way, SAPON arrangement cut-off the short-circuit leakage in the SAFF circuit and prevents the power consumption during transition.

Further, the total power consumption of the proposed SAPON-SAFF compared to the employed Yuan's SAFF can be seen in simulation results of this paper.

In the proposed SAPON-SAFF, Yuan's SAFF [18] is employed; therefore, the working of Yuan's SAFF is as follows:

The SAFF structure proposed in this paper is SAPON-SAFF, shown in Fig. 9. In SAPON-SAFF, like [18], its SA transistors and their connections are kept as it is, except the transistor MN6. Now, two new transistors PMOS type (MTP) and NMOS type (MTN) are connected in SAPON style, outside the logic.

Similar to CONV-SAFF, the SA stage of SAPON-SAFF functions except that, now the pre-charge of the SN and RN is determined by the switching operation of the input D because of the transistors MP5 and MP6 which works in coordination with MN4 and MN5. Thus, SN and RN does not need to be charged to VDD every time when CK is low until the input D switches. MP5 and MP6 cooperate with MN4 and MN5 achieve accurate control of SN and RN, avoiding the continuous charge and

discharge of SN and RN with the CK transition while the input remains unchanged for a long time, avoiding additional power consumption overhead. The always-ON transistor MN3, is used to maintain the output of the SA through SN and RN state, when CK is high. The transistor MN3 offers a path to GND when the data D changes during the positive half cycle of CK. For example, let SN node is discharged to 0 in response to input D = 1 at the rising edge of CK, then SN needs to be maintained at 0 during the positive half cycle of CK. If the input D (at MN4) changes to '0' during the positive half cycle of CK, then another path for '0' should be provided to SN, and hence MN3 works at this time, connecting the path via MN5 with DN (inversion of D), to the GND. And the working of SAPON transistors, MTP and MTN, were already discussed.

In the latch structure of Fig.9 of proposed SAPON-SAFF, the leakage current is effectively avoided because of the transistors MP7, MN7, and MN10. Its inverter-like design ensures the node's fast charge, while the pull-down path design with shut-off transistor MN10 effectively controls the leakage current and ensures the correct function of the latch structure.

This is the working of proposed SAPON-SAFF.

4. SIMULATION AND RESULT COMPARISON:

The proposed SAPON-SAFF has been designed based on MTCMOS-45 nm technology. In order to verify the validity of

the proposed SAPON-SAFF, CONV-SAFF, Nikolic's SAFF, Jeong's SAFF, Heng's SAFF and Yuan's SAFF have also been designed based on the same technology for comparison. Simulation is carried out in Tanner's EDA tool. Simulation schematic in S-Edit tool of the discussed SAFFs, is also represented in the paper. Considering W/L of all NMOS= 130/50nm and of all PMOS= 330/50nm in each design for comparison of simulation results.

T-SPICE with the same settings is adopted to perform all post-layout simulations for comparison. The performance comparisons such as of the average power consumption, CK-to-Q delay, power-delay product (PDP), and area (in terms of number of transistors used) are described in Table.2.

Settings used are:

Power Supply= VDD= 1.0V;

Data Input (in bit) = D= {11001100} (ON=1, OFF=0);

Clock (in bit) = CK= {01010101} (ON=1, OFF=0);

Supply for Y = 1.0V;

Measuring CK-Q DELAY = trigger V(CK) for value=0.025 on fall=1st and target V(Q) for value=0.025 on fall=1st.

Table.2. Post Simulation Comparison of SAPON-SAFF and other SAFFs with CONV-SAFF

SAFF with schematic	AVERAGE POWER CONSUMED	DELAY (CK-Q)	POWER-DELAY PRODUCT (PDP)	AREA (NO. OF TRANSISTORS)
CONV_SAFF [1] Fig. 12(a)	P = 1.182348e-005 watt = 11.823 μ-watt (×1) Max power= 1.389095e-004 at time = 1.05346e-008 Min power= 3.854858e-007 at time = 7.00846e-008	D = -1.0185e-008 = -10.185 n-sec (×1) Trigger = 2.0975e-008 Target = 1.0790e-008	PDP = 120.42 f-J (×1)	20
NIKOLIC'S SAFF [3] Fig. 12(b)	P = 1.236988e-005 watt = 12.37 μ-watt (×1.05) Max power= 1.671182e-004 at time 3.06547e-008 Min power= 7.377143e-008 at time 7.0089e-008	D = 9.6965e-009 = 9.696 n-sec (×0.95) Trigger = 2.0975e-008 Target = 3.0671e-008	PDP = 119.94 f-J (×0.996)	28
STROLLO'S SAFF [5]	P = 6.127042e-005 watt = 61.27 μ-watt (×5.18) Max power = 2.012983e-004 at	D = 2.9579e-008 = 29.58 n-sec (×2.90) Trigger = 2.0975e-008	PDP = 1812.37 f-J (×15.05)	23

Fig. 12(c)	time = 6.07631e-008 Min power = 7.356374e-007 at time = 2e-008	Target = 5.0554e-008		
JEONG'S SAFF [11] Fig. 12(d)	P = 7.632031e-005 watt = 76.32 μ-watt (×6.45) Max power = 2.158840e-004 at time = 1.02499e-008 Min power = 9.096497e-007 at time = 9.12079e-008	D = 9.5652e-009 = 9.565 n-sec (×0.94) Trigger = 2.0975e-008 Target = 3.0540e-008	PDP = 730.00 f-J (×6.06)	25
HENG'S SAFF [14] Fig. 12(e)	P = 3.348426e-005 watt = 33.484 μ-watt (×2.83) Max power = 9.562925e-005 at time = 3.1e-008 Min power = 5.633902e-007 at time = 8.425e-008	D = 1.9881e-008 = 19.88 n-sec (×1.95) Trigger = 2.0975e-008 Target = 4.0856e-008	PDP = 665.66 f-J (×5.53)	22
YUAN'S SAFF [18] Fig. 12(f)	P = 1.068604e-005 watt = 10.686 μ-watt (×0.90) Max power= 1.103219e-004 at time = 6.06004e-008 Min power= 3.526062e-007 at time = 8.00772e-008	D = 1.0002e-008 = 10.00 n-sec (×0.98) Trigger = 2.0975e-008 Target = 3.0977e-008	PDP = 106.86 f-J (×0.887)	25
SAPON-SAFF Fig. 12(g)	P = 3.076407e-006 watt = 3.076 μ-watt (×0.26) Max power = 1.397433e-004 at time = 4.08335e-008 Min power = 6.854698e-008 at time = 2.75331e-008	D = 1.5355e-011 = 15.35 p-sec (×0.0015) = 0.01535 n-sec Trigger = 2.0975e-008 Target = 2.0990e-008	PDP = 0.0472 f-J (×0.00039)	24

Fig.12. Power Consumption Trend in SAFF Designs

Thus, it is clear from Table.2 and Chart of Fig.12, the proposed SAPON-SAFF design achieves a reduction of 73.98% in average power consumption than CONV-SAFF, low CK-Q delay in pico-sec ($\times 10^{-3}$ of CONV – SAFF), and low PDP ($\times 10^{-2}$ of CONV – SAFF). All these parameters shows that the proposed SAPON-SAFF is a low-power, high-speed, and energy efficient SAFF compared to existing SAFFs design.

4.1 SIMULATION SCHEMATICS OF VARIOUS SAFFs

Fig.12(a). CONV-SAFF

Fig.12(b). Nikolic-SAFF

Fig.12(d). Jeong-SAFF

Fig.12(c). Strollo-SAFF

Fig.12(e). Heng-SAFF

Fig.12(f). Yuan-SAFF

Fig.12(g). Proposed SAPON-SAFF

4.2 WAVEFORMS:

Waveform result carried out in W-Edit tool. Waveforms shown here is of CONV-SAFF [1], Yuan’s SAFF [18], and of proposed SAPON-SAFF only, because in the proposed design Yuan’s SAFF [18] is modified.

Fig.13(a). W-Edit waveform of CONV-SAFF of Fig.12(a)

Fig.13(b). W-Edit waveform of Yuan-SAFF of Fig.12(f)

Fig.13(c). W-Edit waveform of SAPON-SAFF of Fig.12(g)

5. CONCLUSION:

This paper proposes a low-power high-speed SAFF. Due to the optimization of the employed Yuan’s SAFF [18] with the SAPON technique [19], a glitch-free and contention-free SAFF design “SAPON-SAFF” is proposed. A new structure for the SA stage in the proposed design minimize the pre-charge power and leakage power of the SAFF. With the employment of the optimized SA stage and the single-ended latch, the delay and power of the SAFF are greatly reduced. The proposed SAPON-SAFF design achieves a reduction of 73.98% in average power consumption than CONV-SAFF, along with low CK-Q delay in pico-sec ($\times 10^{-3}$ of CONV – SAFF) and low PDP ($\times 10^{-2}$ of CONV – SAFF). All these parameters show that, the proposed SAPON-SAFF is a good choice among speed and energy efficient SAFF designs.

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AUTHORS

Ram Yadav is currently a Student of Master of Technology in VLSI Branch of Electronics and Communication Engineering Department at Dr. C. V. Raman University (CVRU), Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh State, India. Prior to this, he completed his Bachelor of Engineering in Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering from Chhattisgarh Swami Vivekananda Technical University (CSVTU), Bhilai, Durg District, Chhattisgarh State, India.

Corresponding Author: Ram Yadav

Pallavee Jaiswal is Assistant Professor in the Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Dr. C. V. Raman University (CVRU), Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh State, India. She received her B.E. Degree in Electronics and Telecommunication

Engineering From GEC, Raipur (C.G.), India & MTech Degree in Digital Communication from Dr. C. V. Raman University, Bilaspur (C.G.), India. She is pursuing her PhD in Electronics and Communication Engineering from Dr. C. V. Raman University, Bilaspur. She is UGC -NET qualified. She has more 10 Years of teaching experience. She has published more than 15 paper in the reputed journals. Her research interests cover Signal Processing, Image Processing, Speech Processing.